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Measurement of the anomalous spin precession frequency ω_a in the Muon $g - 2$ experiment at Fermilab

L. Cotrozzi

Università di Pisa, Italy and INFN Sezione di Pisa, Italy

On behalf of the Muon $g - 2$ collaboration

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Abstract

The muon anomaly, $a_\mu = (g_\mu - 2)/2$, is a low-energy observable which can be both measured and computed to high precision, making it a sensitive test of the Standard Model (SM) and a probe for new physics. The current discrepancy between the experimental value and the Standard Model calculation from the Muon $g - 2$ Theory Initiative [1] is $a_\mu^{exp} - a_\mu^{SM} = (249 \pm 48) \cdot 10^{-11}$, with a significance of 5.1σ . The Fermilab E989 experiment aims, with the full statistical power, to measure a_μ with a precision of 140 parts per billion (ppb), a four-fold improvement with respect to the previous measurement at the Brookhaven E821 experiment (1997-2001). In April 2021 the E989 collaboration at Fermilab National Accelerator Laboratory (FNAL) published our first result, based on the first year of data taking (2018 campaign) [2], and in August 2023 a new result was published, based on the datasets collected during Run-2 and Run-3 (2019 and 2020 campaigns) [3], in agreement with the first result and with the previous experiment at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL). This paper will present details about the improvements and upgrades to the positron reconstruction and to the ω_a analysis since the Run-1 result, and it will describe the final statistical and systematic sources of uncertainty on ω_a in the Run-2 and Run-3 result.

1 The magnetic moment of the muon

The intrinsic magnetic moment of a charged particle with spin is defined by the following relation:

$$\vec{\mu} = g \frac{e}{2m} \vec{S}, \quad (1)$$

where e is the particle charge, m its mass, \vec{S} its spin vector and g the so-called gyromagnetic ratio, a dimensionless parameter. The magnetic moment $\vec{\mu}$ gives us a measure of the torque $\vec{\tau} = \vec{\mu} \times \vec{B}$ and the energy $U = -\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{B}$ that a charged particle experiences in a magnetic field. The Dirac equation predicts the value $g = 2$ for charged particles with spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ such as electrons and muons, but deviations from 2 arise due to radiative corrections in the Standard Model (SM). We can define the magnetic anomaly of the muon as the fractional difference of g_μ from 2: $a_\mu = (g_\mu - 2)/2$.

The anomaly can be decomposed into contributions from different interactions: $a_\mu = a_\mu^{\text{QED}} + a_\mu^{\text{Weak}} + a_\mu^{\text{QCD}}$. The dominant term is the 1-loop quantum electrodynamics (QED) correction to a_μ , equal to $\alpha/2\pi \simeq 0.00116$, where α is the fine structure constant. The hadronic contribution a_μ^{QCD} amounts to ~ 60 parts per million (ppm) and carries the largest uncertainty of ~ 0.40 ppm on the total muon magnetic anomaly. The largest contribution to a_μ^{QCD} comes from hadronic vacuum polarization (HVP) diagrams, where the energy scale is of order of the muon mass, well below the region where QCD can be studied perturbatively: a dispersion relation approach can be used to evaluate the contribution, using the total experimental cross section $\sigma_{tot}(e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons})$ as an input. In 2023, the measurement of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ cross section with the CMD-3 detector evaluated an hadronic contribution to the muon anomalous magnetic moment that was significantly larger than the value obtained from previous measurements [4], and hence it was less in tension with the experimental measurement of a_μ . The origin of the discrepancy between CMD-3 and other experiments is currently not clear. Lattice QCD can also be used to determine the HVP contribution to a_μ using an ab-initio calculation. In 2021, the BMW collaboration presented a prediction of a_μ^{HVP} with the unprecedented uncertainty of 0.8%, which was in tension with the prediction from the dispersion approach [5]. Since then, other groups have been working to confirm or not the BMW result. Figure 1 presents the experimental values of a_μ as measured by BNL E821 [6] and FNAL E989 in 2021 [2] and 2023 [3]. A review of the current theoretical scenario and of the future prospects for the FNAL E989 experiment is presented in Ref. [7].

Figure 1: Experimental values of a_μ from BNL E821 and FNAL E989, and new experimental average. The inner tick marks indicate the statistical contribution to the total uncertainties [3].

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2 Measurement principle of the $g - 2$ experiment at Fermilab

When a particle with spin, with charge e and mass m , is placed in a uniform external magnetic field \vec{B} , it will follow a circular path because of the Lorentz force, with cyclotron frequency ω_C . Its spin will also precess around the direction of the magnetic field, with frequency ω_S . In general, we define the anomalous precession frequency ω_a as the difference between ω_S and ω_C :

$$\vec{\omega}_a = \vec{\omega}_S - \vec{\omega}_C = -\frac{e}{m} \left[a_\mu \vec{B} - a_\mu \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma + 1} \right) (\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{B}) \vec{\beta} - \left(a_\mu - \frac{1}{\gamma^2 - 1} \right) \frac{\vec{\beta} \times \vec{E}}{c} \right]. \quad (2)$$

\vec{E} is the electric field, $\vec{\beta}$ the particle's speed and γ its Lorentz factor. In the Muon $g - 2$ experiment, a spin-polarized beam of muons is injected into a ~ 7 m radius superconducting storage ring, in the presence of a 1.45 T magnetic field, and electrostatic quadrupole (ESQ) plates provide weak focusing for vertical confinement. Ideally, the second term in Eq. (2) vanishes for muons that travel orthogonally to the magnetic field, $\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$, and the third term vanishes for muons with the “magic momentum” $p_\mu \simeq 3.1$ GeV/c, so that $\gamma = \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{a_\mu}} \simeq 29.3$. In this configuration, the expression for the anomalous precession frequency becomes $\omega_a = a_\mu \left(\frac{e}{m}\right) B \simeq 1.43$ rad/ μ s, so a_μ is proportional to ω_a/B . We account for deviations from the ideal case by applying beam dynamics corrections to our measurements. The magnetic field can be expressed by means of the Larmor precession frequency of free protons, via $\hbar\omega_p = 2\mu_p|\vec{B}|$, which is measured with nuclear magnetic resonance techniques. In this paper we will focus on the measurement of ω_a , based on the arrival time distribution of decay positrons in the high-energy tail of the spectrum, detected by calorimeters.

Figure 2: *Left*: Diagram of muon decay in the center-of-mass frame. *Right*: Energy spectrum of emitted positron in $g - 2$ laboratory frame, which changes as a function of the anomalous precession phase.

Due to parity violation in the muon weak decay, high energy positrons are emitted preferentially in the muon's spin direction in the center-of-mass frame (Figure 2, left). As a consequence, in the lab frame the energy spectrum of emitted positrons has a different shape depending on the angle between muon spin and muon momentum, i.e. the anomalous precession phase (Figure 2, right). If we take the integral of the spectrum above a fixed threshold, which corresponds to counting all positrons above a certain energy, we will find a distribution that is modulated by the ω_a frequency, described - in the ideal case - by Eq. (3):

$$N(t) = N_0 e^{-t/\gamma\tau} [1 + A_0 \cos(\omega_a t + \phi_0)], \quad (3)$$

where N_0 is a normalization parameter, A_0 the amplitude of the oscillation, ϕ_0 the initial phase, and $\gamma\tau$ is the muon lifetime in the lab frame, ~ 64.4 μ s. We choose a threshold of 1.7 GeV that minimizes the statistical uncertainty on ω_a with this method. In the so-called “Asymmetry-weighted” method, instead, we lower the threshold to 1.0 GeV and apply appropriate weights to our data to further reduce the statistical uncertainty [8].

3 Positron detection and reconstruction

Positrons that are emitted from muon decay have a smaller orbit radius than the muon beam, thus they curl towards the center of the ring where they are detected. There are 24 electromagnetic calorimeters placed around the inner radius of the storage ring, which measure the energies and arrival times of incident positrons. Each segmented calorimeter features a 6×9 array of PbF_2 (lead fluoride) crystals, which absorb the energy of incoming positrons that generate a contained electromagnetic shower and produce Cherenkov photons. Each crystal is coupled to

a silicon photomultiplier (SiPM), which responds to Cherenkov photons with electrical current; this current is then converted into voltage signal by a custom electronic board, recorded by waveform digitizers and stored for offline analysis. A laser calibration system sends simultaneous pulses onto each of the 1296 crystals, to monitor the SiPM gains at the level of 0.04% during the 700 μs window in which muons are stored, and also on the timescales of days and months to correct for long-term effects, such as temperature changes [9].

Figure 3: *Left*: Trace of a positron hitting a crystal, fitted with a predetermined template to obtain the time and deposited energy of the event. *Right*: Energy spectra of clusters before pileup correction: old Run-1 clustering (blue) compared with the new Run-2/3 clustering (red), which reduces the number of unresolved pileup events after ~ 3.1 GeV.

To reconstruct the energy and arrival time of detected positrons, we perform a template fit on the waveforms of each crystal hit, as shown in the example in Figure 3 (*left*). We then reconstruct positron events from their energy deposition in multiple crystals, and fill a two-dimensional histogram in energy and time. When two or more positrons hit the same calorimeter very close in time, the reconstruction algorithm is not always able to separate the two events and the incident particles are reconstructed as a single hit. This is the “pileup effect” and it introduces a systematic bias in the ω_a analysis because it distorts the measured energy and time spectra in a time-dependent way: the rate of double events is the square of the rate of detected positrons, so it has a lifetime of $\sim 32 \mu\text{s}$. By studying the time distribution of clusters, we estimate the number of double and triple pileup events that need to be corrected for. In Run-2 and Run-3, we have improved our clustering algorithms to the degree shown in Figure 3 (*right*): we compare the energy spectra of positrons before pileup subtraction between the old and the new clustering, where values above the maximum physical energy of 3.1 GeV are present. With the new, improved clustering, we were able to reduce the number of unresolved pileup events by a factor of ~ 3 . After pileup subtraction, the spectra are mostly flat and near zero after 3.1 GeV, and any residual events in the unphysical region are accounted for with systematic studies.

4 Precession frequency analysis: fit to “wobble plots”

From the pileup-corrected energy and time distribution of the positrons, there are different methods to build the histograms used to extract the anomalous precession frequency ω_a : this paper will focus on the “Threshold method” (T-Method) which was commonly used amongst most analysis groups. The time distribution of detected positrons above the 1.7 GeV threshold is shown in the inset plot of Figure 4 (*left*), and it is called “wobble plot” due to its shape. In principle, we can perform a very simple fit with the 5 parameters of Equation (3): N_0 , $\gamma\tau$, A_0 , ω_a and ϕ_0 . A more complicated function takes into account many beam dynamics effects: for instance, the radial and vertical motion of the muons in the plane transverse to the storage ring, or the muons that scatter away, typically because they interact with collimators or because the injection angle differs from the design value. Figure 4 (*left*) shows the fit to Run-3 data and

the fast fourier transform (FFT) of the residuals: the red dashed curve shows peaks at all the frequencies that are not accounted for in the 5-parameter fit; the solid black curve is the FFT when fitting with the full function, which removes all residual frequencies.

Figure 4: *Left*: FFT of residuals from the wiggler plot fit (inset plot) in the case of 5-parameter function (dashed red) or complete fit function in Run-3 (solid black). *Right*: decoherence of the CBO term as a function of time after muon injection, in Run-2.

In the full fit, the dominant term is the coherent betatron oscillation (CBO). The muon beam in the storage ring oscillates radially with frequency $\omega_x \simeq 40 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{s}$, faster than the cyclotron frequency, so the wavelength of the radial oscillation is greater than the ring circumference. Each of the 24 calorimeters samples the positron distribution at a fixed location, so the rate at which the muon bunch moves with respect to the detector is the aliased CBO frequency: $\omega_{\text{CBO}} \equiv \omega_C - \omega_x \simeq 2.32 \text{ rad}/\mu\text{s}$. Figure 4 (*right*) shows the amplitude of the CBO term in Run-2 data, which reduces over time because the betatron oscillations are an ensemble of frequencies and they decohere with a lifetime of the order of 100 μs .

5 ω_a systematics and improvements in Run-2 and Run-3

There are many sources of systematic uncertainties to ω_a , most of them related to how well we know the parameters used in positron reconstruction, such as pileup subtraction or energy calibration, or to how well we understand the beam dynamics effects in our time distributions. In Run-1, the biggest systematic contributions to ω_a were pileup, which amounted to 35 parts per billion (ppb), and CBO that contributed for 38 ppb. The total uncertainty on ω_a was 434 ppb due to statistics and 56 ppb from systematic effects [10]. In Run-2 and Run-3, there were many hardware and software improvements to reduce the systematics. For instance, in Run-1 there were damaged resistors in the ESQ system, which strongly affected the beam dynamics by inducing large changes in the betatron frequencies over the muon storage window of 700 μs . These resistors were repaired before the start of data taking in Run-2; in addition, the non-ferric fast kicker system was fixed towards the end of Run-3 to provide a stronger kick to the muon beam and facilitate its centering. These improvements greatly reduced many systematic effects related to beam dynamics. In Run-2 and Run-3 combined, we collected 4.7 times the statistics than in Run-1, which more than halved the statistical uncertainty and also allowed us to improve our empirical modeling of the CBO decoherence envelope and reduce the associated systematic from 38 ppb to 21 ppb. On the reconstruction side, as explained in Section 3, we improved our algorithms to better resolve pileup. We also developed new techniques of pileup removal, e.g. overlaying crystal waveforms instead of modeling the reconstruction response to pileup as we did in Run-1, reducing the total systematics due to this effect from 35 ppb to 7 ppb.

Total uncertainties [ppb]	Run-1	Run-2/3
ω_a statistical	434	201
ω_a systematic	56	25
Major Run-1 systematics [ppb]	Run-1	Run-2/3
CBO	38	21
Pileup	35	7

Table 1: Statistical and systematic uncertainties on ω_a from Run-1 to Run-2/3.

Table 1 shows the factor ~ 2.2 reduction in both ω_a statistical and systematic uncertainties, from Run-1 to Run-2/3. More details are available in Ref. [3].

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